

RUMĚNÍK

103

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This is the first issue of the magazine Ruměník. Its name comes from a forgotten Czech National Revival variant for the element rhodium – from a time when Czech patriots sought to create “new Czech” names for words of German origin.

That is why this inaugural issue is dedicated to that era and to the discovery of rhodium itself. This year marks 222 years since it was first described by William Hyde Wollaston.

The main part of this issue is a pictorial dedicated to rhodium and its many facets. My own project also carries Rh in its name, making this element a natural focus of my work.

At the end of this issue, you will also find a glimpse of what I am currently working on in connection with Rh.

Happy Birthday, Rhodium!
Miloš Večeřa

Happy Birthday, Rhodium

PtRh thermocouple

**Spark plug with an
iridium tip (Rh-doped)**

Catalyst – Alumina/Rh

**Cut piece of Rh sheet
from X-ray technology**

**Three-way catalyst –
PGM-doped ceramic**

**Native platinum from
Colombia (polyxene containing
Rh) with locally cemented gold**

**Native iridium from Alaska
with minor Rh content**

Rhodium – pinkish-red

**Rhodium black,
freshly precipitated metal**

250
ml

SIMAX
CZECH REPUBLIC

**Organometallic rhodium
compound, intended for X-ray
analysis**

**Organometallic rhodium
compound, crystal**

**My current research:
luminescence of Rh complexes**

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Next issue?
Czech native gold

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- in honor of rhodium and its light.**